

TERM BARBARISMS AND THEIR PLACE IN MODERN UZBEK TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract: *The article addresses the issues related to the use of terms, including their impact on linguistic identity and the need to find Uzbek equivalents. The study aims to understand the role of term-barbarisms in the context of globalization and cultural interaction, as well as to develop recommendations for optimizing the use of borrowed terms and maintaining linguistic purity.*

Key words : *term-barbarism, linguistics, computer, forum, chat*

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Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются проблемы связанные с использованием терминов, включая их влияние на языковую идентичность и необходимость поиска узбекских эквивалентов. Исследование направлено на понимание роли термин-варваризмов в контексте глобализации и взаимодействия культур, а также на выработку рекомендаций по оптимизации использования заимствованных терминов и сохранению языковой чистоты.*

Ключевые слова: *термин-варваризм, лингвистика, компьютер, форум, чат*

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TERMIN-VARVARIZMLAR VA ULARNING ZAMONAVIY O‘ZBEK TERMINOTIZIMIDA TUTGAN O‘RNI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada atamalardan foydalanish bilan bog‘liq muammolar, jumladan, terminning o‘ziga xosligiga xususiyati va o‘zbekcha ekvivalentlarini izlash zaruriyati ko‘rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot globallashtirish va madaniyatlarning o‘zaro ta‘siri sharoitida termin-varvarizm rolini tushunishga, shuningdek, o‘zlashtirilgan atamalardan foydalanishni optimallashtirish va til sofligini saqlash bo‘yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: termin-varvarizm, tilshunoslik, kompyuter, forum, chat

Introduction

Barbarisms refer to borrowed terms that are actively used in a language but originate from foreign sources and often retain elements of the original language. In modern Uzbek, such terms can emerge as a result of adopting new concepts, technologies, or ideas, particularly in the fields of science, technology, business, and culture. Throughout different historical periods, the Uzbek language has been influenced by various cultures and languages, such as Arabic, Persian, Russian, and English. These borrowings often introduced terms that either preserved their original forms or were adapted to Uzbek phonetics. The use of barbarisms can have both positive and negative effects. On one hand, they facilitate the understanding and integration of modern concepts. On the other hand, excessive use of such borrowings may lead to the loss of traditional terms and pose challenges for those who do not know foreign languages. In official and academic texts, there is often an effort to find Uzbek equivalents for borrowed terms. However, in practical usage, especially in professional and technical fields, original terms remain widely used. Future trends will depend on changes in international politics, economics, and technology, as well as efforts to standardize and normalize Uzbek terminology. It is essential to balance the need to integrate new concepts with the preservation of linguistic identity and traditions. Barbarisms in Uzbek terminology are a significant aspect of the language, reflecting globalization and the development of modern society.

Literature Review

Y.M. Fedosova, in her classification of pedagogical terms in the process of learning the Russian language, identifies three groups: Fully assimilated terms, i.e., terms adopted according to the norms of the recipient language: аудит (audit), стейкхолдер (stakeholder), квест (quest), теппинг-тест (tapping-test), актив-тренинг

(active-training), фишбоун (fishbone), бинго (bingo); Partially assimilated lexical units: ревитализация (revitalization), дуальное (образование) (dual), пролонгация (prolongation), валидность (valid), реферирование (referring), публикация (publication), рефлексия (reflection), инклюзивное (образование) (inclusive), дефиниция (definition); Barbarisms: OPI (Oral Proficiency Interview), TOEFL (Test of English as a Foreign Language). [1] Accordingly, Y.V. Smathina divides incoming terms into such groups as fully transliterated (acquired according to the existing spelling rules of the recipient language), harmonized (partially adapted), and non-transliterated (taken as is). [6]

In Uzbek linguistics, Kh. Dadaev emphasizes the problems of term assimilation.

Methods

The most common method of enriching a terminological system with the necessary terms, as in the lexical system of a language, is the adoption of terms. Information about the genesis of a specific term or terminological system in the language, the factors that prompted its emergence, its conceptual and categorical foundations, etymology, history, quantity, and types is of great importance. This is because the development of specialized vocabulary cannot be conceived separately from the development of its respective field; that is, the terminology of a specific domain does not evolve in isolation from other factors. It depends on both intralinguistic and extralinguistic factors. Therefore, studying borrowed terms allows linguists to gather rich material about a specific people, their interaction with other nations during different historical periods, cultural-historical traditions, and value systems, providing grounds for interlinguistic lexical exchange. For example, the development of the education sector in a country and education reform have played a role, alongside intralinguistic factors, in shaping Uzbek terminology for distance education. Additionally, changes in sociopolitical life, the pandemic (e.g., the spread of the coronavirus infection), the development of communication technologies, the emergence of new generations of electronic tools, the level of computerization and informatization in the country, and other extralinguistic factors have contributed to this process. Linguistics identifies several methods for term assimilation, a subject that has always attracted the attention of linguists and terminologists. The incorporation of a foreign word from another language into the lexicon of a specific field is a natural process, but ensuring its phonetic, graphic, orthographic assimilation, terminological formalization, nationalization, and socialization within the language remains a significant challenge.

In modern terminology, four main methods of term assimilation are distinguished: 1) Direct assimilation; 2) Assimilation through a donor language; 3) Assimilation

through calquing; 4) Assimilation without adaptation to the norms of the recipient language.

Analysis and Results

Currently, using the example of Uzbek terminology for distance education, we will examine our analysis of terms borrowed into Uzbek specialized terminology through direct adoption, donor languages, calquing, or without adaptation to the existing norms of the Uzbek language, particularly focusing on barbarisms. A relatively large portion consists of terms borrowed directly, either fully or partially adapted to the phonetic, grammatical, and orthographic norms of the Uzbek language: *forum* – форум, *chat* – чат, *messenger* – мессенджер, *professor* – профессор, *lecturer* – лектор, *tutor* – тьютор, *advisor* – эдвайзер, *coach* – коуч, *master* – магистр, *bachelor* – бакалавр, etc. Based on this, the assimilation of terms is considered one of the most important ways to stabilize and systematize terminology.

The assimilation of new terms through other methods is somewhat problematic, leading to an excessive number of barbarisms, terminological variations, duplicate terms, polysemy, synonymy, and illogical terms in the vocabulary of the field. In particular, terms borrowed from donor languages, such as those adapted to the phonetic, graphic, morphological, and orthographic norms of Russian, constitute the majority in modern terminology and result in terminological variations. For example, the abbreviation *HEMIS* (Higher Education Management Information System), denoting a system for managing higher education processes, was borrowed into Uzbek from the phonetic and graphic features of the Russian language as *Хемис*. Other examples include *hyperlink* – гиперссылка, гипертекст, based on partial calquing. Additionally, terms such as *wiki technology* – Вики-технология, *keys study* – кейс-стади, *website* – веб-сайт, *web camera* – веб-камера, *Office Manager* – офис-менеджер, *offline lecture* – офлайн-лекция, *internet service provider* – интернет-провайдер, were also borrowed through intermediary languages and written according to the orthological norms of Russian.

Through calquing, including full calquing (*distance learning* – дистанционное обучение (D-learning), *blended learning* – смешанное обучение (B-learning), *authoring tools* – программный продукт, *Electronic mail (e-mail)* – электронная почта, *educational program* – образовательная программа, *Academic program* – учебная программа, *Learning management system* – системы, управляющие процессом виртуального обучения, *asynchronous learning* – асинхронное обучение, *core subjects* – основные предметы, etc.); partial calquing (*web training* – веб-обучение, *credit-hour* – кредит-часы, *online course* – онлайн курс, *online*

school – онлайн школа, *educational content* – образовательный контент, *hyperlink* – гиперссылка, *mobile learning (m-learning)* – мобильное обучение, *electronic learning (e-learning)* – электронное обучение); and terms assimilated through semantic calquing (*e-teacher* – онлайн учитель, *instructor* – онлайн учитель, *summary* – краткое содержание предмета, *syllabus* – рабочая программа предмета, *transcript* – академический справочник, *grades* – информация об оценках), also make up a significant portion of the modern terminological system.

Discussion

In terminology, foreign terms that enter a language without full transliteration are also prevalent, and it has become common to consider them as barbaric terms or linguistic barbarisms. [1]

What is a barbarism? Barbarism (from Greek *barbarismos*; Latin *barbaros* – foreign) refers to words or expressions not fully assimilated into a language, used as foreign linguistic elements. Typically, they are employed to describe a foreign language, notions of nationality, customs, to create local color, or to emphasize a character's affiliation with another language. [2] For this reason, barbarisms are often used alongside exosystems. [3] Depending on the language they originate from, barbarisms can be categorized as Anglicisms (from English), Americanisms (from American dialects), Gallicisms (from French), Germanisms (from German), and Polonisms (from Polish).

In specialized vocabulary, as in general vocabulary, all forms of barbarisms can be found. Term-barbarisms are lexical units that are not adapted to the phonetic or graphic norms of the recipient language, fully preserving both their external material form and internal structural content. Term-barbarisms are largely alien elements in the language, and their presence is considered a negative phenomenon for linguistic integrity.

The emergence of barbaric lexical terms in texts related to specific sciences or technologies is due to the following reasons:

1. The rapid influx of terms does not allow them to be fully adapted to the norms of the recipient language immediately or included in dictionaries, leaving their orthological form undefined.
2. Not all industry representatives can determine or transliterate the graphic form of these borrowings, leading to their continued usage in texts without boundaries.
3. The attempt to preserve the graphic form of a term from its source language to indicate its genesis or etymology, as part of the scientific style, or when necessary, provide a translation in parentheses in Uzbek.

4. The lack of an alternative term in the national language to fill the lexical gap, among other reasons.

One of the characteristic features of 21st-century Uzbek terminology is the expansion of the language through term-barbarisms borrowed without assimilation. Such terms can be found in all specialized sources and, most concerning, in political publications and legal documents: *usell*, *Beeline*, *e-mail*, *Viber*, *Twitter*, *Skype*, *Chevrolet Cobalt*, *YouTube*, *SmartApe*, *Chrome*, *Galaxy*, *SHAREit*, *Wi-Fi*, *Bluetooth*, *Screenshots*, *Google*, *WhatsApp*, *iPhone*, *Windows*, *COVID-19*, *URL*, *SMS*, *MMS*, *Scopus*, *Times New Roman*, *Microsoft Word*, *LMS*, *Moodle*, *CMS*, *HTML*, *VPS*, *NVMe*, *SSD*, *Zoom*, *Hemis*, etc.

For example, in the online publication *daryo.uz*, the headline “Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a meeting with the heads of the companies *AMEA Power*, *SWC*, *Air Products*, and *Tadweer*” [4] contains foreign language text such as *AMEA Power*, *SWC*, *Air Products*, and *Tadweer*. Similarly, in the publication *New Uzbekistan*, the phrase “The President of Uzbekistan met with the company *SWS* to discuss the implementation of infrastructure projects” [5] includes terms like *SWS*, which are considered barbarisms.

The assimilation of terms requires studying not only their graphic, phonetic, and morphological aspects but also the stages of transliteration — the processes of adoption. It is necessary to consider the point of interaction between the incoming and receiving languages, as well as factors such as nationality, social status, gender, level of language proficiency, and the purpose of adoption.

In Uzbek linguistics, K. Dadabayev, emphasizing the challenges of term assimilation, highlights the following points:

1. the diversity of approaches to the acceptance and assimilation of scientific and technical terms borrowed from foreign languages;
2. the use of ready-made words available in the lexical stock of Uzbek dialects alongside the literary language to express specific objects, concepts, and events;
3. the effective use of word-formation affixes in the Uzbek language for creating terms;
4. significant attention given to the formation of terms through derivational patterns;
5. the incorporation of foreign terms into the Uzbek terminological system without employing any of the aforementioned methods. [7]

The pandemic accelerated the transition to global education, including distance learning in our country, to such an extent that most terms in this field began to be perceived as barbarisms—adapted to the graphic, phonetic, or orthographic norms of the language being adopted. This clearly provides grounds to conclude that there

should currently be no domain in the Uzbek terminological system where distance learning operates using terms adopted based on barbarisms or semi-calques. This situation has led to several problems concerning the understanding and application of these terms even by specialists in the field. Due to other factors associated with this process—phonetic-phonemic and graphic changes, as well as orthographic errors—borrowing has resulted in the habit of allowing inconsistent spelling of terms.

In modern Uzbek, the following manifestations of barbarized terms are observed:

Assimilated terms that have completely retained their original graphic form: E-learning, D-learning, M-learning, B-learning, SCORM, Moodle, on-line, Forums Skype, Forum, WebTutor, Microsoft Teams, Edgenuity, Materials, Messenger, Chat, Exercises, Group work, Student tracking, IMS, Apache, IIS, Windows, Linux, Mac OSX, Novell Netware, Moodle LMS.

Partially graphically adapted terms that have not been fully transliterated into Uzbek, are not widely used in the literary language, and have not yet been socialized: Google, WhatsApp, internet, podcast, smiley, gadget, casting.

Syntactic barbarisms, which are part of foreign syntactic constructions in the form of phrases: open-source Moodle software suite, iSpring platform, LMS WebTutor platform, Teachbase Cloud-based learning platform, GetCourse info-Business platform, Memberlux platform for WordPress, web service, Word document, Excel spreadsheet, web hosting service, MySQL, PostgreSQL, PHP processor, QR-code.

Overall, Anglicisms—borrowings from English—are being integrated into the terminology of not only the Uzbek language but also other languages around the world at an extraordinary pace. In the context of terminology for distance learning, it is evident that the majority of specialized vocabulary consists of barbarized terms borrowed from English or mediated through it.

The above observations highlight the necessity of establishing strict criteria when determining the orthological form of borrowed terms in Uzbek. In particular, the scientific justification for specific orthographic forms of terms related to distance learning requires careful attention to the following aspects:

1. Consideration of the phonetic, pronunciation, and graphic features specific to the recipient language during the adoption of terms. To avoid the emergence of barbarized terms that involve the use of multiple vowels or letters such as *w* and *c*, which are absent in the Uzbek alphabet, the written form of borrowed terms should align with the presence or absence of corresponding sounds and letters in the recipient

language's alphabet. This can be achieved through a collaborative approach in defining each new orthographic form of a term, involving specialists from several fields—experts in English, linguists, lexicographers, IT specialists familiar with the modern linguistic norms of Uzbek, as well as educators working in distance learning.

2. The orthographic form of the current written Uzbek language does not align with graphical styles that are uncharacteristic, such as the use of uppercase letters in different parts of a word. Borrowed terms like iSpring, Hi-Tech, SHAREit, WhatsApp, MySQL, PostgreSQL, WordPress, GetCourse, PowerPoint, WebTutor, Wi-Fi should be transliterated in a manner that avoids graphical irregularities when forming orthographic terms. According to modern scientific norms of the Uzbek language, only proper nouns are written with an uppercase letter, and initials appear only at the beginning of a word. The capitalization of all components of compound nouns is governed by specific spelling rules and does not apply in such cases.

3. Consideration must be given to the differences in orthographic rules for writing compound and abbreviated words in English and Uzbek. In English, the first word is often written with a hyphen in abbreviations (e.g., e-learning, D-learning, m-learning, B-learning, e-teacher, e-mail Archive, e-educational, e-instructor, e-Mentor), and similar patterns have influenced Uzbek usage (e.g., e-minbar, e-imzo, e-pochtasi, where the first letter refers to the abbreviation "e"). To address these inconsistencies, it is advisable to introduce standardized translations for these terms into scientific discourse. For instance:

e-minbar → electronic platform

e-imzo → electronic signature

e-pochtasi → email

e-instruktor → e-instructor

Conclusions

Although the assimilation of terms is a natural process, it becomes a negative phenomenon for a language when the majority of terms within a specific terminological system consist of borrowed elements rather than native ones. The nationalization of terms and the expansion of the Uzbek language's use in scientific fields are among the priorities for developing the state language. At the same time, the widespread adoption of borrowings and barbarized terms in terminology cannot, of course, be justified.

Borrowed lexical units that remain unassimilated in Uzbek—i.e., barbarized terms—retain their ontological properties, which are uncharacteristic of the receiving

language in both pronunciation and writing. Consequently, they remain alien to the new linguistic environment, both in external form and internal content. These terms are fundamentally foreign elements to the language, and their unrestricted use shows a lack of respect for the receiving language as well as disregard for domestic intellectuals, educators, and linguists.

Thus, the emerging issues regarding the orthography and structural and grammatical characteristics of terms being assimilated into the Uzbek language necessitate elevating research in this field to a new qualitative level—shifting from the descriptive stage of terminological studies to a prescriptive and recommendation-based approach.

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